

Enhancing Energy Access in Malawi through Off-grid and Grid Integrated Renewables

Alfred Kampira Levison

Malawi University of Science and Technology

Malawi

29th July 2025

Keywords: Off-Grid, Integrated, Malawi, Access, Scale-Up, OSeMOSYS, Energy System.

Acknowledgements

First and foremost, I acknowledge the support of my trainers under OSeMOSYS Rakia Bouallegui and Monikah Kitili without which this report wouldn't be here. I remain indebted to Climate Compatible Growth for financing my trip and International Centre for Theoretical Physics for the excellent hosting. All Global Energy Modelling Platform funders including World Bank Group, IAEA, IEA, Sustainable Energy for All among others for making EMP-G 2025 a reality. This material has been produced with support from the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme. CCG is funded by UK aid from the UK government. However, the views expressed herein do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies.

Executive Summary

Malawi has an estimated population of 21 million people. However only 30-40% of this population has access to electricity. This report explores the potential of off-grid and grid-integrated renewable energy systems in enhancing energy access in Malawi, a country currently facing low access and an unreliable grid system. Using the open-source modelling tool OSeMOSYS, three scenarios are evaluated: Baseline/Business-As-Usual (BAU), Access Demand Increase (ADI), and Off-grid Scale-Up (OGS). The key findings indicate that the ADI scenario can achieve 60% electricity access by 2030 using the current energy mix with moderate investments. The OGS scenario, aligned with the Malawi Renewable Energy Strategy, showcases a significant shift toward off-grid solar and biomass, supporting Malawi's National Energy Policy goals and contributing to Sustainable Development Goal 7.

1. Introduction

Malawi's energy sector is dominated by high reliance on hydropower, and widespread use of traditional biomass for cooking and other household energy needs (Chisale & Lee, 2023). Approximately 35-40% of the population has access to electricity, with rural areas particularly underserved. Statistics indicate that over 85% of rural Malawians have no access to electricity. Figure one below showcases the current energy profile in Malawi and the associated percentage of each technology. The reliance on biomass has led to deforestation and indoor air pollution. In response, the Malawi National Electrification Strategy & Action Plan targets over 60% access by 2030, with a mix of grid expansion and mini grids. The Regulatory Framework for Mini grids (2019) in Malawi targets at least 50 operational mini-grids by 2025 (MERA, 2019.).

This study therefore investigates how renewable energy, specifically off-grid solar and grid-integrated biomass and other renewables, can improve energy access, meet the specified demand, and reduce emissions. The objective is to determine the most cost-effective and sustainable pathways for achieving universal access while aligning with Malawi National Energy Policy and Agenda 2063. policies and international commitments such as SDG 7 and Agenda 2063.

Figure 1: Energy Profile in Malawi

2. Methodology

The study employs the Open-Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS), a widely used bottom-up linear optimization tool for long-term energy planning. Version 5.3 of OSeMOSYS was used. The tool allows for cost-effective technology deployment decisions based on defined scenarios and constraints. In this study, a Reference Energy System (RES) for Malawi was designed and used to simulate Malawi's energy profile from 2021 to 2050 in five-year intervals. The procedure involved data collection, model calibration, validation, scenario design and results analysis.

The data for model design was obtained from multiple sources including the Malawi National Electrification Strategy & Action Plan (2022), Malawi Renewable Energy Strategy (2017) and National Energy Policy (2018) which provided policy related information on the energy scenario in Malawi. The system installed capacities were obtained from the Selected 'Starter Kit' energy system modelling data for Malawi (Carla Cannone, 2021). Further, technology cost and performance data were obtained from IRENA, Electricity Supply Corporation of Malawi (ESCOM), Electricity Generating Company (EGENCO), Malawi Energy Regulatory Authority (MERA), Ministry of Energy and other local agencies.

Scenarios

The study involved 3 scenarios which were modelled sequentially starting with the baseline scenario or business-as-usual (BAU) to assess demand increase (ADI) scenario

which aimed at identifying the systems potential in meeting a 60% increase using current reservoirs. Lastly, an Off-Grid Scale-Up (OGS) scenario was run to scale up solar off-grid systems and biomass power plants in-line with Malawi Renewable Energy Strategy and subsequently manage emissions. Table 1 below describes the scenarios, the key assumptions made and the analysis.

SCENARIO TITLE	DESCRIPTION	KEY ASSUMPTIONS
Baseline Scenario (BAU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maintenance of the current installed capacities with minimal intervention and free flow. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business as usual with the model freely optimizing the system on top of the maintained installed capacities
Access Demand Increase Scenario (ADI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increasing access to electricity to 60% by 2030 according to Malawi National Electrification Strategy & Action Plan using current mix [4] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electricity Energy demand to be used as an indicator to access-RES. Current mix potentially capable of meeting the demand.
Off-grid Scale-up Scenario (OGS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scaling-Up Off-Grid access to meet the growing demand in-line with Malawi Renewable Energy Strategy (2017) and Regulatory Framework for Mini-grids at least >50 operational MG by 2025 [3]. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The vast solar potential in Malawi estimated at a daily average of 4.2kWh/m² capable of meeting the demand [5]. Traditional Biomass replaced with low to no emissions

Table 1: OSeMOSYS Scenarios

3. Results

Production by Technology

The BAU scenario maintains dominance of hydropower with over 85% with the current installed capacity with minimal diversification. The ADI scenario demonstrates capability to meet the up-scaled 60% demand, largely using hydroelectricity and a share of nuclear, biomass, diesel and solar. The OGS scenario significantly shifts the energy mix by scaling up off-grid solar and biomass while also utilizing a share of hydro to diversity the mix, reduce diesel usage and aligning with Agenda 20263 on reducing heavy reliance on hydroelectricity (GoM, 2020). Figure 2 shows the production of power by technology across the simulated range.

Figure 2: Production by Technology

Accumulated New Capacity

The figure 3 below shows the accumulated new capacity of the three scenarios. The BAU and ADI rely primarily on expanding hydropower. A great share of investment is

seen in hydro to meet the upscaled demand. On the other hand, OGS emphasizes solar PV and biomass, offering a more diversified and resilient energy portfolio. The orange key for off-grid solar in the figure below shows how much of hydro has been replaced by Off-grid solar intuitively. The OGS model further shows the quick cutting of diesel power to full venture into renewables.

Figure 3: Accumulated New Capacities

Investment Costs:

Annual investment in the ADI scenario remains moderate but increases steadily. Emissions are slightly higher than BAU but still within manageable levels. In contrast, OGS requires higher initial investments but achieves lower emissions, driven by clean energy technologies.

Figure 4: Investment Costs

Emissions

The total annual emission shows a reduction as the model progresses. The Baseline model gradually gets rid of emission by 2029. This is also the situation for ADI Scenario. However, the OGS model promptly cut off emissions by the year 2027 with net-zero emissions in the proceeding years. Figure 5 shows the total annual emissions for all the three case scenarios.

Figure 5: Total Annual Emissions

4. Discussion

The results provide critical insights into the pathways for achieving Malawi's energy access goals and diversifying its energy mix. The ADI scenario demonstrates that 60% access is achievable by 2030 using existing technologies and infrastructure as proposed by the Malawi National Electrification Strategy & Action Plan. This is evident through the scenario meeting the specified demand which translates to access. However, the continued reliance on hydropower poses environmental and reliability concerns, especially under increasing climate risks. Furthermore, the system also uses diesel generators to supplement its grid which emits emissions hence the need for an OGS scenario.

The OGS scenario illustrates how a diversified energy mix, emphasizing solar and biomass, can reduce emissions and improve reliability. The OGS model utilizes Malawi's policy and vast solar potential of about 1715kWh/year/m² to power up the country with over 50% of demand met by renewables and particularly solar off-grid systems (Levison, 2024). This scenario aligns closely with Malawi's National Energy Policy (2018), which calls for increased renewable energy investments and a transition away from traditional biomass (Policy, 2018). It also supports the regulatory framework for mini grids, aiming for over 50 operational sites by 2025 and the Malawi Vision 2063 which aims at reducing hydro-electricity reliance by 2040 (GoM, 2020).

The model assumes static policy environments and constant technology costs. It further may be limited due to data limitations. Nevertheless, it provides a strong foundation for forecasting and a platform for further studies on detailed socio-economic impact assessments of mini-grid deployments in Malawi and exploration of storage technologies for the achieved solar mini grids.

5. Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that both grid-integrated and off-grid renewable systems can significantly enhance energy access in Malawi using OSeMOSYS to optimize the most economical and sustainable pathway. While the ADI scenario provides a cost-effective pathway using existing resources, the OGS scenario presents a more sustainable, low-emission alternative that aligns better with national policy and international energy goals. In the future work, the model aims to expand on specific policy parameters to guide the calibration and simulation.

6. References

- Carla Cannone, L. A., Ioannis Pappis et al. (2021). 'Starter Kit' energy system modelling data for Malawi (#CCG). *Research Square PREPRINT (Version 2)*.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-479507/v2>
- Chisale, S. W., & Lee, H. S. (2023). Evaluation of barriers and solutions to renewable energy acceleration in Malawi, Africa, using AHP and fuzzy TOPSIS approach. *Energy for Sustainable Development*, 76, 101272.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esd.2023.101272>
- GoM. (2020). Malawi's vision 2063: An Inclusively Wealthy and Self-reliant Nation. [Online]. Available: <https://malawi.un.org/sites/default/files/2021-01/MW2063-%20Malawi%20Vision%202063%20Document.pdf>
- Levison, A. K., Nasruddin, Wongani Ziba. (2024). Investigating the Potential of Building-Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV) for Powering Public Buildings in Malawi. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 6. <https://theacademic.in/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/38.pdf>
- MERA, G. a. (2019.). Regulatory Framework for Mini-grids. [Online]. Available: https://www.energy.gov.mw/wp-admin/admin-ajax.php?juwpfisadmin=false&action=wpfd&task=file.download&wpfd_category_id=27&wpfd_file_id=1898&token=a28faa1b57dc4bb4ea3057e2622ea075&preview=1
- Policy, G.-N. E. (2018). *Malawi National energy policy*. Retrieved from <https://www.energy.gov.mw/wp-admin/admin-ajax>